

BASIC WAYS OF SELF-STUDY FORMATION TO STUDENTS

Istamova Shohista

Teacher of the department of English History and Grammar Samarkand State
Institute of Foreign Languages
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10868813>

Annotation. Information is readily available everywhere today. The greatest way for a person to utilize the information is to get it on their own. Many students supplement their classroom studies by studying at home. We refer to this as self-study. A great way to improve the studying process is through independent study. It is a teaching strategy in which pupils learn at their own pace, outside of the classroom, with minimal or no direct supervision. We will explore how self-study ties help to study efficiently as well as the greatest self-study ties since self-studying is increasingly becoming a popular approach to advance studying.

Key words: *self-study, setting goals, self development, online studying, productivity, games, apps.*

Introduction

It is not always necessary that a student understands what has been taught when they study in class or attend a lecture. Self-study becomes crucial because of this. Self-studying enables students to learn more than what is taught to them in traditional textbooks and by their professors. Additionally, it encourages students to dig deeper into areas that interest them, enhancing their ability to learn and their study habits.

The importance of self-study for students are follows:

- Self-study gives students a sense of understanding to determine what they should study and how to study based on their own capacity.
- With effective self-study tips, students can make their own notes and study them in the language they are most comfortable with.
- Self-study helps boost a student's confidence. It satisfies their need and allows them to study freely.
- Self-study heeles students take studying at their own pace, helping in focusing on areas they are most interested in.
- Self-studying helps lessen the frustration, anxiety, or boredom that students may struggle with within a classroom setting.
- Self-studying allows students to choose something they are excited to learn about, leading to a more engaging and effective studying experience.

No matter how many hours you spend in a coaching facility, school, or distant online course, it is impossible to retain what you hear from your teachers unless you also do independent research on the subject.

Self-study is an essential component of any preparation. Self-studying is not just about reading for an hour every day. Your study sessions become more productive and effective as a result. Unrealistic goals might result in disappointment and a laid-back attitude. When developing self-study habits, it's crucial to choose a schedule that logistically fits with your obligations. You can plan and establish a goal for achievement by, for instance, scheduling time to read one chapter each day. Setting goals allows you to know how much effort you have to do and learn how to adjust your schedule to avoid a busy one. It provides you with mental relaxation so that you can learn things well.

Reading the same textbooks over and over again might get boring and hinder your studying and productivity. However, including several teaching methods into your studying stimulates various brain regions and encourages studying behaviors. It can be used a variety of tools to learn and become more productive in today's digital world. In addition to reading textbooks and class notes, you can broaden your knowledge by utilizing online studying tools including eBooks, test series, and video tutorials.

It can be better understood what students have learned in school and what subjects fascinate you if you are capable of self-realization. It will motivate students to push yourself to learn more and explore the world, keeping you ahead of the classroom curriculum. There are many different ways to learn. Self-realization enables you to recognize what is crucial for you to learn and how to maximize your studying.

Increased productivity and effectiveness will result from doing so. Consider that your course offerings include areas like science, math, social science, English and computers. Instead of allocating one week to each subject, it is preferable to study two or three subjects every day to increase production in each. The best way to retain knowledge is to take notes. It enables the brain to take in and digest the data that students gather while studying. As soon as you finish reading a chapter or a subject, make handwritten notes. By doing this, you may quickly refer back to that note if you forget any information. You can increase your familiarity and understanding of the particular subjects in this way.

Students cannot immediately improve your performance through self-studying. You must constantly evaluate yourself. You have no way of knowing

how much of what you read in textbooks and class notes you have actually retained and absorbed. Self-assessment becomes crucial in this situation. Instead of waiting for formal tests or exams, you should test yourself right away. You can assess your skills by completing puzzles, quick tests, finishing sample papers, taking mock exams, etc. It will assist you understand your progress and discover your stronger and weaker areas that need to be fixed.

Educational games have been shown to enhance the self-studying process. There are several apps available that are based on every subject. For instance, you may access these apps through your phones and answer problems in more engaging ways if you want to make math exciting and intriguing. The fact that educational games encourage studying, engage students in their subjects, and enhance knowledge retention is one of their greatest benefits.

Games and quizzes are a fascinating and innovative aspect of educational gaming. The greatest way to remember any text is to read it aloud. When you read aloud a book, you hear it as well as see it. You can better concentrate on the idea this way. There is a chance that you will forget something you learned because you were thinking more clearly when you read aloud because all you can see is the text.

It has been demonstrated that taking brief breaks while studying increases focus and efficiency. Instead of spending hours sitting still, schedule your study time over a period of 40 to 60 minutes. After that, you must take a break for 10 to 15 minutes to walk around, speak with someone, etc. Setting alarms to remind yourself to take breaks and continue studying according to the timetable is a smart idea. Many times, students even skip meal breaks that are bad for their health.

Conclusion

Individual work is therefore one of the most important topics that are widely discussed in the field of education at secondary schools and higher educational institutions from the perspective of modern pedagogical science and social requirements. The study employed the following methodologies: classification and generation; historical and pedagogical observation (in the course of training sessions, consultations, and departmental methodological workshops); and study documentation.

References:

1. Karimova U., Istamova S., Nyoman T. D. P. I. AIM OF LINGUISTIC TYPOLOGY AND DIFFERENT APPROACHES TO THE SUBJECT //Models and methods in modern science. – 2023. – T. 2. – №. 13. – C. 73-76.

2. Shohista I. THE ROLE OF JIGSAW TECHNOLOGY IN DEVELOPING LEARNERS' AUTONOMY //CURRENT RESEARCH JOURNAL OF PEDAGOGICS. – 2023. – Т. 4. – №. 11. – С. 114-116.
3. Shohista I. et al. THEORETICAL BACKGROUND AND CURRENT ISSUES IN ENGLISH LANGUAGE LEARNING //American Journal of Research in Humanities and Social Sciences. – 2023. – Т. 11. – С. 146-149.
4. Sh I. RECENT TRENDS AND ISSUES IN ENGLISH LANGUAGE TEACHING //Экономика и социум. – 2023. – №. 4-2 (107). – С. 118-120.
5. Abdullayev A., Imansyah A. THE WAYS OF WORD-FORMATION IN ENGLISH LANGUAGE //Current approaches and new research in modern sciences. – 2023. – Т. 2. – №. 12. – С. 5-9.
6. <https://goo.gl/images/TBg8c7>
7. <https://goo.gl/images/3ETNrs>

